

The Open Book Concept

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INTRODUCTION

I was inspired with Leonard E. White (PhD, Duke University) on-line lectures (seen at coursera.org) about the rule of brainstem nuclei localization, so I would like to suggest here a new name for this rule: **The Open Book Concept**.

The rule of brainstem nuclei localization explains that general somatic motor and branchial motor nuclei are the closest to the midline of the brainstem (middle of the book); general visceral motor nuclei are lateral from somatic and branchial motor nuclei; visceral sensory and special visceral sensory nuclei are more lateral than general visceral motor nuclei; somatic sensory and special somatic sensory nuclei are the most lateral nuclei in the brain stem.

Image 1.0. Introduction to the Open Book Concept.

Chapter One: Mesencephalon (Midbrain)

Image 1.1. Chapter One: Mesencephalon (Midbrain).

General somatic efferent (motor) nuclei in the midbrain are the oculomotor nucleus and the trochlear nucleus. The oculomotor nucleus is located in the upper part of the midbrain at the level of the superior colliculus. The oculomotor nuclei (left and right sides) form a single complex that lies in the central grey matter, ventral to the cerebral aqueduct (of Sylvius). The oculomotor nucleus sends fibers (oculomotor nerve) to supply the superior, medial and interior rectus, inferior oblique and levator palpebrae superioris muscles. The trochlear nucleus is located in the lower part of the midbrain at the level of the inferior colliculus. The nucleus lies anterior to the cerebral aqueduct in the central grey matter. It sends fibers to innervate the superior oblique muscle.

General visceral efferent (motor) nucleus in the midbrain is the accessory oculomotor nucleus (Edinger-Westphal nucleus). Fibers arising in this nucleus pass through the oculomotor nerve, and relay in the ciliary ganglion to supply the sphincter pupillae and the ciliary muscle.

Chapter Two: Pons

Image 1.2. Chapter Two: Pons.

General somatic efferent (motor) nucleus of the pons is the abducens nucleus that lies in the lower part of the pons, deep to the facial colliculus in the floor of the fourth ventricle. It is situated in the grey matter lining the floor of the fourth ventricle near the midline. It sends its attached nerve to supply the lateral rectus muscle.

Special visceral efferent (motor) nuclei (branchial efferent, branchiomotor nuclei) of the pons are the nucleus of the facial nerve and trigeminal motor nucleus. The nucleus of the facial nerve lies in the lower part of the pontine tegmentum, anterolateral to the nucleus of the abducens nerve. It sends fibers that loop around the abducens nucleus and emerge ventrolaterally at the pontomedullary junction. The looping axons form the genu of the facial nerve which is responsible of the smooth hump that protrudes into the fourth ventricle (facial colliculus). The facial motor nucleus contains motoneurons that innervate the facial muscles of expression that are derived from the second

branchial arch. The motor nucleus of the trigeminal nerve lies in the upper part of the pons, in the pons' dorsal part. It is situated in the lateral part of the reticular formation, medial to the main sensory nucleus of the trigeminal nerve. The motor nucleus of trigeminal nerve innervates the mastication muscles, mylohyoid muscle and tensor palati muscle.

General visceral efferent (motor) nuclei of the pons are the salivatory nuclei. The superior and inferior salivary nuclei lie in the dorsal part of the pons, just above its junction with the medulla. They are located a little above the upper end of the dorsal nucleus of the vagus nerve. The superior salivatory nucleus sends fibers into the facial nerve and these fibers relay in the submandibular ganglion to supply the submandibular and sublingual salivary glands. The inferior salivary nucleus sends fibers into the glossopharyngeal nerve. Those fibers relay in the otic ganglion to supply the parotid gland. The parotid gland may also receive some fibers from the superior salivatory nucleus, through the submandibular ganglion.

Chapter Three: Medulla Oblongata

Image 1.3. Chapter Three: Medulla Oblongata.

General somatic efferent (motor) nucleus of the medulla oblongata is the hypoglossal nucleus that is situated near the midline and below the hypoglossal trigone (triangle) in the floor of the fourth ventricle of the upper medulla. It is an elongated column extending into both the open and closed parts of the medulla. It sends motor fibers that innervate the muscles of the tongue.

Special visceral efferent (motor) nuclei (branchial efferent, branchiomotor nuclei) of the medulla oblongata are spinal accessory nucleus and nucleus ambiguus. The nucleus ambiguus forms an elongated column lying deep in the reticular formation, both in the open and closed parts of the medulla. Inferiorly, it is continuous with the spinal accessory nucleus. The nucleus ambiguus is a composite nucleus and contributes fibers to the glossopharyngeal, vagus and accessory nerves. The eleventh nerve (accessory nerve) has two parts. The smaller cranial part arises from cells in the nucleus ambiguus and ultimately is distributed with the vagus nerve. This portion innervates the

pharyngeal muscles. The main part, the spinal portion, arises from a long column of nuclei situated in the ventral part of the medulla and extending to the fifth cervical segment or lower. As the fibers leave the cord they join together and ascend through the foramen magnum, then leave through the jugular foramen with the vagus nerve. The nerve descends in the neck near the jugular vein and supplies the sternocleidomastoid and trapezius muscles, joined by motor or sensory contributions from the upper cervical nerves.

General visceral efferent (motor) nucleus of the medulla oblongata is the dorsal motor nucleus of the vagus nerve (dorsal vagal nucleus). It is long and it lies vertically in the medulla. Its upper end lies deep to the vagal trigone in the floor of the fourth ventricle. When traced backwards, it extends into the closed part of the medulla where it lies in the lateral part of the central grey matter. Fibers arising from the dorsal vagal nucleus supply the heart, lungs, bronchi, esophagus, stomach, small intestine and large intestine up to the right two-thirds of the transverse colon. These fibers end in ganglion (nerve plexuses) closely related to above mentioned organs.

General and special visceral afferent (sensory) nucleus of the medulla oblongata is the nucleus of the solitary tract. Its cells form an elongated column lying deep in the reticular formation. The nucleus solitarius receives fibers carrying general visceral sensations through the vagus and glossopharyngeal nerves. It also receives fibers from geniculate ganglion of the facial nerve. Through those afferents, and through connections with the reticular formation, the nucleus of solitary tract plays an important role in the reflex control of respiratory and cardiovascular functions. Fibers of taste (special visceral afferent), varied by facial, glossopharyngeal and vagus nerves end in the upper part of the nucleus of the solitary tract. This upper part of the nucleus is referred to as the gustatory nucleus.

Special somatic afferent (sensory) nuclei of the medulla oblongata are the cochlear and the vestibular nucleus. There are two cochlear nuclei: dorsal and ventral cochlear nucleus. They are positioned dorsal and anterior to the inferior cerebellar peduncle at the level of the junction between the pons and medulla. The two nuclei are continuous with each other, being separated only by a layer of nerve fibers. The vestibular nucleus is situated partly in the medulla and partly in the pons. Four distinct nuclei of the vestibular nucleus are recognized: medial, lateral (Deiter's nucleus), inferior and superior vestibular nuclei.

Chapter Four: The Longest Nuclear Complex of the Brain Stem

Image 1.4. Chapter Four: Trigeminal complex.

General somatic afferent (sensory) nuclei of the brain stem are also known as the trigeminal complex, the longest nuclear complex of the brain stem.

The mesencephalic nucleus of the trigeminal nerve extends cranially from the upper end of the main sensory nucleus in the pons into the midbrain. This nucleus appears to be similar to sensory ganglia of the cranial nerves, and to the spinal ganglia. The processes (dendrites) of the neurons of this nucleus are believed to carry proprioceptive impulses from muscles of mastication, and possibly also from muscles of the eyeballs, face, tongue and teeth. The mesencephalic nucleus is the center for jaw jerk. The main (principal) sensory nucleus of the trigeminal nerve lies in the upper part of the pons, in the lateral part of the reticular formation. It lies lateral to the motor nucleus of the trigeminal nerve. The superior sensory nucleus is mainly concerned in mediation of proprioceptive impulses, touch and pressure. The spinal nucleus of the trigeminal nerve extends from the main nucleus (superior sensory nucleus) in the pons down into the medulla, and into the

upper two segments of the spinal cord. The lower end of the spinal nucleus is continuous with the substantia gelatinosa of the spinal cord. The spinal nucleus receives general somatic sensations carried by the facial, glossopharyngeal and vagus nerves. Functions of the spinal nucleus includes mediation of pain and thermal sensibility.

CONCLUSION

In the middle of the book (in the middle of the brainstem) there are somatic motor and branchial motor nuclei. **Therefore, general somatic motor and special visceral motor nuclei are closest to the middle of the book (brainstem).** More lateral are general visceral motor nuclei. Lateral from general visceral motor nuclei are visceral sensory and special visceral sensory nuclei. The most lateral nuclei in the brainstem are general somatic sensory and special somatic sensory nuclei. **Therefore, the general and special somatic sensory nuclei are on the edge of the book pages (the most lateral nuclei of the brainstem).**

Motor nuclei are located medially, whilst sensory nuclei are located laterally. Efferent nuclei are located medially, whilst afferent nuclei are located laterally. Somatic nuclei are both the most medial and the most lateral nuclei, whilst visceral nuclei are in between.

REFERENCES

1. <https://www.coursera.org/learn/medical-neuroscience/lecture>: Leonard E. White, PhD, Duke University.
2. Aghoghovwia B. Cranial nerve nuclei. Reviewed by Mytilinaios D. October 5, 2021. Retrieved from <https://www.kenhub.com/en/library/anatomy/cranial-nerve-nuclei> (cited on October 27, 2021)
3. Walker HK. Cranial Nerve XI: The Spinal Accessory Nerve. In: Walker HK, Hall WD, Hurst JW, editors. Clinical Methods: The History, Physical, and Laboratory Examinations. 3rd edition. Boston: Butterworths; 1990. Chapter 64. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK387/> (cited on October 27, 2021)
4. Sherwood CC. Comparative anatomy of the facial motor nucleus in mammals, with an analysis of neuron numbers in primates. *Anat. Res.* 2005; 287A:1067-1079.
5. Images are created in Power Point.